

WORK ENGAGEMENT, ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT, AND EMPLOYEE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMS OF RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT COMPANIES IN METRO MANILA: BASIS FOR EMPLOYEE RETENTION FRAMEWORK

Edward Jan Paul E. Ebreo

Lyceum of the Philippines University - Batangas, Batangas City, Batangas, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13581580>

ABSTRACT

By employing both descriptive and correlational methodologies, the study aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research and development companies specifically from three pharmaceutical companies in Metro Manila. The descriptive research design focused on systematically collecting data to describe the situation and three host pharmaceutical institutions engaged in research and development. Supplementing the descriptive approach, the correlational research design aimed to quantify the relationships between variables or sets of scores. This involved identifying variables of work engagement, organizational commitment and employee development programs, and their interrelationships to ascertain potential significant correlations. Results revealed that there was strong evidence for both work engagement and organizational commitment while moderate evidence for employee development programs. These variables have significant connections with each other. Based from the findings, the proposed employee retention framework may be used to improve the employee retention at research and development companies especially within the pharmaceutical industry. Future researchers may use other variables that could have similar effects on the work engagement of research and development companies especially within the pharmaceutical industry.

Keywords: *Work Engagement, Organizational Commitment, Employee Development Programs, Employee Retention Framework*

INTRODUCTION

Employee retention within an organization is intricately linked to various factors (Chaudhary, 2023). In the context of an organization, job characteristics, and individual attributes collectively influence the inclination of employees to remain with their current organization. Factors within the organization encompass elements such as the organizational culture, leadership style, opportunities for advancement, compensation and benefits, work-life balance initiatives, and overall organizational climate (Andrianto & Alsada, 2019). Similarly, job-related factors incorporate the nature of the work, amount of work, autonomy, task variety, prospects for skill utilization, and inherent rewards.

Behavioral intentions and inclinations of the employee precede how an employee acts in their organization posited by the Theory of Reasoned Action (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). Individual employee attributes which comprise attitudes, values, motivations, and career objectives exercise significant influence on employees' decisions regarding retention within an organization. It also becomes evident that employees' intentions to remain with their current organization are critical to determining their subsequent actions. Thus, when individuals observe a coherence between their personal goals, work characteristics, and work environment, they are more inclined to show actions and behaviors indicative of their intention to stay with their organization (Silva, et al., 2023).

In essence, employees are more likely to commit when they believe that their values align with those of the organization, when they feel a supportive work culture, and when they perceive a sense of autonomy and control over their work environment (Nguyen, et al., 2020). This alignment nurtures a sense of belonging and fulfillment, enhancing employees' commitment and reducing turnover rates. Moreover, when employees feel that their professional aspirations are acknowledged and supported by the organization, they are more likely to invest in their long-term growth within the company, further solidifying their intention to stay.

Additionally, an organization's efforts to enhance job fulfillment, provide opportunities for skill development, and create a positive work culture can significantly contribute to reinforcing employees' intentions to remain with the organization (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). Therefore, understanding and addressing individual attributes and aligning them with organizational objectives are crucial strategies for promoting employee retention and fostering a committed and engaged workforce. Thus, employee retention emerges as a dynamic process influenced by the interplay of organizational, job-related, and personal-related factors, wherein employees' intentions serve as a precursor to their retention-related actions (Rasdi & Chen, 2018).

Employee retention and effective people management are essential factors in maintaining a competitive edge and sustaining economic growth in the Philippines (Malinao & Agustin, 2022). In a dynamic and competitive job market like the Philippines, where the economy is rapidly expanding, retaining talented employees has become more

critical than ever for businesses striving to thrive amidst fierce competition. Businesses need to recognize that their workforce is one of their most valuable assets, and losing skilled employees can significantly impact productivity, innovation, and overall success. Therefore, investing in strategies to attract, engage, and retain top talent is crucial. This includes offering competitive compensation and benefits packages, providing opportunities for career development and advancement, fostering a positive work culture that values diversity and inclusivity, and implementing effective performance management and employee recognition programs. By prioritizing employee retention and people management initiatives, businesses in the Philippines can not only reduce turnover costs but also create a sympathetic and conducive environment where employees feel valued, motivated, and committed to achieving organizational goals, ultimately driving success and sustainability in the research and development sector.

Research and development (R&D) play a multifaceted and essential role in an economy's growth, innovation, and competitiveness. The economic research in the field of econometrics consistently demonstrates that, irrespective of the diverse methods used it is typically observed that a substantial and statistically meaningful enhancement in productivity and economic expansion is seen as a result of increased investment in research and development (OECD, 2015). R&D endeavors yield novel technologies, goods, and procedures. By increasing the productivity, efficiency, and competitiveness of industries, these innovations can promote economic growth. The Philippine business companies have been severely affected by the COVID-19 pandemic hence, there is a need to strengthen employee retention within the organizations in the country (Caredo, et al., 2022). There are also a few studies specific to the research and development industry of the country, a sector that can help in the economic growth of the Philippines. Employee retention within this sector has been a point of contention among employees and organizations for several reasons and this point of contention has to be addressed.

The R&D sector in the Philippines, specifically the pharmaceutical industry, is significant as it is one of the sectors that provides hope to alleviate health and well-being of the people, not only in the country, but in a more global scale. Employee retention within this sector is vital as it aids in keeping the goals of the organization (Andrianto & Alsada, 2019). The implications of the study are imperative within the three host institutions/organizations within the sector in the Philippines. However, these implications maybe applicable to other organizations in a global scale.

The outcomes of R&D initiatives ripple through the economic landscape, fostering a climate ripe for growth and ingenuity. This is accentuated by strong empirical evidence within the field of econometrics, consistently underscoring the tangible benefits of increased R&D investments within an economy of a country (Olaoye, 2021). The infusion of resources into research and development not only fosters novel technologies but also births groundbreaking goods and refined processes. These advancements act as pivotal agents which amplifies productivity and competitiveness across various sectors (Szarowská, 2018). Consequently, the resultant surge in economic growth becomes a

testament to the indispensable role that R&D plays in steering the course of a thriving and dynamic economy.

In an interconnected and technologically evolving world, each of the countries recognize the crucial role of R&D in maintaining a competitive edge and achieving sustainable economic growth. Investments are strengthened in the R&D sector to promote innovation, improve productivity, and advance various sectors, including healthcare, technology, and manufacturing (Soltanisehat, et al., 2022). The economic benefits of R&D are not restricted to amplified production; they extend to job creation, higher living standards, and long-term economic growth. The transformative impact of R&D reverberates through different industries; redefining norms of the economic landscapes.

Entrenched within the canons of econometrics exhibits a resounding affirmation of the correlation between intensified investment in research and development and positive economic advancement (Szarowská, 2018). The outcomes are made apparent in various forms of revolutionary technologies, pioneering products, and streamlined methodologies. These advancements become the foundation for increased productivity, improved efficiency, and heightened competitiveness within sectors, shaping a conducive environment for sustained economic growth and laying the groundwork for continued innovation and advancement.

The emphasis on R&D is not limited to economic growth; it also extends to addressing pressing challenges in various sectors. R&D plays a critical role in finding solutions to complex problems, from healthcare to environmental sustainability. By investing in R&D, the government aims to stimulate innovation, drive economic growth, and enhance the quality of life for its citizens. It is a strategic investment in the future, a commitment to finding solutions to the most intricate challenges that transcend national borders. R&D serves as a beacon of hope, a testament to human ingenuity, and a testament to the unwavering dedication to a better, more sustainable, and healthier world.

This sector is one of the priorities of the Philippine government as this is highlighted in the Philippine Development Plan 2023-2028. R&D sector is seen as a vital pillar of economic progress and a clear sector to build up in the country (NEDA, 2023). The R&D sector in the Philippines is a dynamic and growing part of the country's economy and academic landscape. It encompasses a wide range of activities, organizations and industries focused on scientific and technological advancement. As a result, the country has seen an exponential growth in research initiatives and academic collaborations.

In the medical and pharmaceutical context, R&D companies contribute to the development of various new drugs, devices and solutions aimed to address medical quandaries (Shabani, et al., 2022). This is essential to address medical challenges, advance public health and entice investment into the health sector. The transition from R&D to the pharmaceutical industry is a crucial driver that delivers development of life-

saving procedure, equipment, and drugs. The combination of scientific discovery, clinical development and regulatory approval is a complex path that promises to improve human health and countries' economies (Varntanian, 2018). As research continues to advance and new breakthroughs emerge, synergy between R&D and the pharmaceutical industry will remain essential to solving healthcare challenges and driving innovation.

The Philippine pharmaceutical industry includes a wide range of companies, both local and multinational. Local companies such as United Laboratories (Unilab), Pascual Laboratories and others operate alongside global pharmaceutical giants such as Pfizer, GlaxoSmithKline (GSK), Sanofi-Aventis, and others (Reyes & Taguba, 2020). These companies are involved with developing, manufacturing, distribution and marketing of pharmaceutical products, including prescription and over-the-counter drugs, medical devices and various healthcare-related products. The Philippines is one of the major pharmaceutical markets in the ASEAN region only trailing to Indonesia and Thailand (BOI, 2017). Roughly 4.4% of the top 500 Non-Individual Taxpayers in the Philippines are pharmaceutical companies according to the Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR) contributing P15.7 Billion in taxes in 2011 alone (NTRC, 2014).

Research on employee retention in pharmaceutical companies engaged in R&D is of particular importance due to the unique and important nature of this field. It is true that employee retention is a key challenge in any sector; it creates a challenging situation in balancing an organization's ability financial and knowledge resources (Patriota, 2009). The pharmaceutical R&D sector is marked by its inherent complexity, the importance of innovation and its significant dependence on qualified experts. There are only a very small number of studies on the profile of the Philippine pharmaceutical industry; the majority of works deal with market research, association reports, and drug prices (Reyes & Taguba, 2020). Employee retention extends beyond the conventional realms of human resource management. It is inherently tied to the industry's ability to innovate, remain competitive, and respond to evolving healthcare hurdles (Alkafafy & Siddiqui, 2022). Moreover, the loss of specialized experts on respective fields can ultimately undermine the pharmaceutical industry's ability to bring innovative resolutions.

Research Questions

The purpose of this to study is to assess the work engagement, organizational commitment and employee development programs of research and development companies in Metro Manila as basis for an employee retention framework. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. assess work engagement their employees in terms of vigor (physical), absorption (cognitive), and dedication (emotional) engagement;
2. determine their organizational commitment as affective, normative and continuance commitment;

3. evaluate the employee development and training programs of the Pharmaceutical companies in terms knowledge /skills retention, significance of programs, and employees' appreciation / satisfaction;
4. test the correlation among work engagement, organizational commitment, and employee development programs; and
5. lastly, develop an employee retention framework.

METHODOLOGY

The participants of the study were employees from the three (3) host pharmaceutical companies engaged in research and development in Metro Manila. They were from different positions and roles in different pharmaceutical companies. Samples were randomly obtained across the three pharmaceutical companies and the survey participants of the study totaled four hundred twenty-eight (428). Participants also had a diverse range of age salaries, educational attainment and years of service. As per the confidentiality agreement, the number of participants from each host institutions was not revealed.

As there were no current data on the number of employees in pharmaceutical companies in Metro Manila at the time of writing, the researcher used the latest available data from the Philippine Competition Commission's Issue Paper published in 2020. The number of employees totaled one thousand four hundred two (1,402). The number of pharmaceutical companies totaled twenty (20) based on the official published account of the country in 2020.

The study used four sets of questionnaires (first would be the profile of the respondents) as the primary instrument in collecting the necessary data from the respondents. Items in the instrument were presented as descriptive statements, and respondents were given the frequency with which each of the descriptive statement applies on a four-point Likert scale with an interpretation of 3.50 – 4.00 scale means strongly agree, 2.50 – 3.49 rate means agree, 1.50 – 2.49 scale means disagree and, 1.00 – 1.49 rating means strongly disagree.

The questionnaire was composed of two parts. The first part contained the profile of the respondents from the pharmaceutical companies. The second part, on the other hand, contained the assessment of work engagement, organizational commitment and employee development programs of their host institution. Work engagement is a three-factor model consisting of physical engagement (5 items) with Cronbach alpha of 0.830, cognitive (5 items) with Cronbach alpha of 0.808, and emotional engagement (5 items) with Cronbach alpha of 0.798. For this variable, questions totaled 15 items.

Measuring organizational commitment was materialized and tabulated through the instrument adopted to the study of Kassaw & Golga (2019) which standardized it. This

study applies a four-point Likert scale. It was a 15-item questionnaire with three factors; affective commitment (5 items) with Cronbach alpha reading of 0.854, continuance commitment (5 items) with alpha reading of 0.823 and normative commitment (5 items) with Cronbach alpha reading of 0.823.

Lastly, in assessing parts of employee development programs, the questionnaire was adopted from a previous study that proposed a (Hajjar & Alkhanaizi, 2018). It applied a four-point likert scale with verbal interpretation of 3.50 – 4.00 scale means strongly agree (with great evidence), 2.50 – 3.49 rate means agree (with moderate evidence), 1.50 – 2.49 scale means disagree (with little evidence) and, 1.00 – 1.49 rating means strongly disagree (without evidence). It was a 15-item questionnaire with three factors; knowledge/skills retention with a Cronbach alpha reading of 0.826, significance of programs with an alpha reading of 0.791, and employees' appreciation/satisfaction with an alpha reading of 0.785.

Cronbach's alpha was used by the authors to test the reliability of the adopted instrument. This statistical method provides a coefficient that quantifies the degree to which items within a test consistently measure the same underlying construct (Jugessur, 2022). It was used under the assumption the researcher has multiple items measuring the same fundamental concept to guarantee the reliability and consistency of their measurement instruments, thereby fortifying the credibility of their study outcomes. A strong Cronbach's alpha value, typically falling within the 0 to 1 range which signals an internal consistency, signifying a high correlation among variables and a reliable measurement of the targeted concept (Taber, 2018). The researcher of this study used the published theses and dissertations as sources for the gathering and collection of data. In addition to these, books, articles and peer-reviewed journals that are reliable for the study were used where relevant data and related information will be collected. Additional and relevant information on the pharmaceutical companies were collected through informal interviews.

Before gathering of the data, it was reiterated to the host institutions that the purpose of the survey to be conducted will be used for academic purposes and that all information collected will be kept confidential. Upon the approval of the respective heads of departments of the research and development companies, specifically from the pharmaceutical industry, and approval of the adopted questionnaires by the adviser, the researcher started by distributing questionnaires to the staff of the three (3) selected pharmaceutical companies in Metro Manila engaged in research and development.

The schedule for the date of distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire was discussed and set on a mutually agreed date with the pharmaceutical companies. The questionnaires were administered by using google forms as per the request of the host institutions. To ensure the accuracy and confidentiality of the results, limited people handled the survey results.

Weighted mean and rank were used to assess work engagement their employees in terms of vigor (physical), absorption (cognitive), and dedication (emotional) engagement; to determine their organizational commitment as affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuance; and to evaluate the employee development and training programs of the Pharmaceutical companies in terms Knowledge/skills retention, significance of programs, and employees' appreciation/satisfaction. The result of Shapiro-Wilk Test showed that p-values of all variables were less than 0.05 which means that the data set was not normally distributed. Therefore, Spearman rho was used as part of the non-parametric tests to determine the significant relationship. All analyses were performed using SPSS version 28.

RESULTS

Table 1
Work Engagement in terms of Physical Engagement

Indicators	WM	VI	Rank
1. I recognize the importance of reporting for work	3.66	Strongly Agree	1
2. I am willing to participate in the activities at work	2.65	Agree	4
3. I keep active in my workplace	3.39	Agree	2
4. I am enthusiastic about work and doing my duties	2.61	Agree	5
5. I put a lot of effort when it comes to achieving my tasks at work	2.96	Agree	3
Composite Mean	3.05	Agree	

Legend:3.50-4.00=Strongly Agree;2.50-3.49=Agree;1.50-2.49=Disagree;1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree

Table 2
Work Engagement in terms of Cognitive Engagement

Indicators	WM	VI	Rank
1. I finish the task assigned at work in a timely manner	3.78	Strongly Agree	2
2. I understand my role and responsibilities at work	2.85	Agree	4
3. I understand how my work contributes to the overall goal of the institution	2.92	Agree	3

4. I am able to decide on the best course of action to finish my assigned task	3.80	Strongly Agree	1
5. It is difficult to detach myself from my job	2.62	Agree	5
Composite Mean	3.19	Agree	

Legend:3.50-4.00=Strongly Agree;2.50-3.49=Agree;1.50-2.49=Disagree;1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree

Table 3
Work Engagement in terms of Emotional Engagement

Indicators	WM	VI	Rank
1. I see professional growth and career development opportunities for myself in the institution	3.29	Agree	3
2. I am happy and satisfied with my current work/job	3.43	Agree	2
3. I have good working relationship with my co-workers	3.04	Agree	4
4. I get a sense of personal accomplishment when I do my work and tasks	3.51	Strongly Agree	1
5. I am inspired by my work to do better	2.83	Agree	5
Composite Mean	3.22	Agree	

Legend:3.50-4.00=Strongly Agree;2.50-3.49=Agree;1.50-2.49=Disagree;1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree

Table 4
Summary Table on Work Engagement

Key Result Areas	Composite Mean	VI	Rank
Physical Engagement	3.05	Agree	3
Cognitive Engagement	3.19	Agree	2
Emotional Engagement	3.22	Agree	1
Grand Composite Mean	3.15	Agree	

Legend:3.50-4.00=Strongly Agree;2.50-3.49=Agree;1.50-2.49=Disagree;1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree

Table 5
Organizational Commitment as Affective Commitment

Indicators	WM	VI	Rank
1. I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career in this organization.	3.42	Agree	2
2. I really feel as if this organization's problems are my own.	2.97	Agree	3
3. I feel this organization makes me feel like I am part of a family.	3.70	Strongly Agree	1
4. I feel that I am "emotionally attached" to this organization.	2.93	Agree	4.5
5. I have a strong sense of belonging in my organization	2.93	Agree	4.5
Composite Mean	3.19	Agree	

Legend:3.50-4.00=Strongly Agree;2.50-3.49=Agree;1.50-2.49=Disagree;1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree

Table 6
Organizational Commitment as Normative Commitment

Indicators	WM	VI	Rank
1. It would be very hard for me to leave my job at this organization right now even if I wanted to.	3.60	Strongly Agree	2
2. Different aspects of my life would be affected if I left this organization.	2.93	Agree	5
3. I believe that staying with this organization is a matter of necessity and desire.	3.19	Agree	4
4. I believe I have not enough options to consider leaving this organization.	3.99	Strongly Agree	1
5. Leaving this organization would require a considerable personal sacrifice from me is one of the reasons why I continue to work here.	3.23	Agree	3
Composite Mean	3.39	Agree	

Legend:3.50-4.00=Strongly Agree;2.50-3.49=Agree;1.50-2.49=Disagree;1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree

Table 7
Organizational Commitment as Continuance

Indicators	WM	VI	Rank
1. I do not feel it would be right to leave even if leaving would be better for me.	3.38	Agree	3
2. I would have a feeling of guilty if I left this organization now.	3.40	Agree	2
3. This organization deserves my loyalty.	2.94	Agree	5
4. I would not leave my organization right now because of my sense of obligation to it.	3.51	Strongly Agree	1
5. I owe a great deal to this organization.	3.08	Agree	4
Composite Mean	3.26	Agree	

Legend:3.50-4.00=Strongly Agree;2.50-3.49=Agree;1.50-2.49=Disagree;1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree

Table 8
Summary Table on Organizational Commitment

Key Result Areas	Composite Mean	VI	Rank
Affective Commitment	3.19	Agree	3
Normative Commitment	3.39	Agree	1
Continuance	3.26	Agree	2
Grand Composite Mean	3.28	Agree	

Legend:3.50-4.00=Strongly Agree;2.50-3.49=Agree;1.50-2.49=Disagree;1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree

Table 9
Employee Development Programs in terms of Knowledge and Skills Retention

Indicators	WM	VI	Rank
1. I find the learnings from previous programs still applicable today	2.79	Agree	4
2. I learned new skills from programs instituted by my organization	3.37	Agree	1
3. I still use skills I've learned from previous programs	2.77	Agree	5
4. I apply things I learn from the programs of my institution	2.81	Agree	3

5. I value the knowledge and skills I gain from my organization's programs	3.24	Agree	2
Composite Mean	3.00	Agree	

Legend:3.50-4.00=Strongly Agree;2.50-3.49=Agree;1.50-2.49=Disagree;1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree

Table 10
Employee Development Programs in terms of Significance of Programs

Indicators	WM	VI	Rank
1. I find the programs in my organization highly relevant to my work	2.87	Agree	4
2. I find the programs in my organization are utilizable even outside my work	3.12	Agree	3
3. The programs in my organization aid me while doing tasks at work	3.35	Agree	1
4. The programs in my organization aligns my expectations to that of my organization	2.82	Agree	5
5. The programs in my organization addresses my needs and that of others to be more efficient and effective at performing my tasks	3.24	Agree	2
Composite Mean	3.08	Agree	

Legend:3.50-4.00=Strongly Agree;2.50-3.49=Agree;1.50-2.49=Disagree;1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree

Table 11
Employee Development Programs in terms of Employees' Appreciation

Indicators	WM	VI	Rank
1. I feel empowered after attending the employee development programs of my organization	2.81	Agree	5
2. I am confident with performing my tasks after attending the programs of my organization	3.17	Agree	2
3. The programs of my organization make me feel like I am part of the future of my organization as it prepares me for other tasks	3.23	Agree	1

4. I am satisfied with the work I am doing and I feel like I am growing professionally when I attend the programs of my organization	3.06	Agree	4
5. The programs of my organization help decide into staying with my organization	3.08	Agree	3
Composite Mean	3.07	Agree	

Legend:3.50-4.00=Strongly Agree;2.50-3.49=Agree;1.50-2.49=Disagree;1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree

Table 12
Summary Table on Employee Development Programs

Key Result Areas	Composite Mean	VI	Rank
Knowledge and Skills Retention	3.00	Agree	3
Significance of Programs	3.08	Agree	1
Employees' Appreciation	3.07	Agree	2
Grand Composite Mean	3.05	Agree	

Legend:3.50-4.00=Strongly Agree;2.50-3.49=Agree;1.50-2.49=Disagree;1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree

Table 13
Relationship Between Work Engagement and Organizational Commitment

Variables	rho	p-value	Interpretation
Physical Engagement			
Affective Commitment	0.862**	<.001	Highly Significant
Normative Commitment	0.407**	<.001	Highly Significant
Continuance	0.462**	<.001	Highly Significant
Cognitive Engagement			
Affective Commitment	0.833**	<.001	Highly Significant
Normative Commitment	0.462**	<.001	Highly Significant
Continuance	0.584**	<.001	Highly Significant
Emotional Engagement			
Affective Commitment	0.456**	<.001	Highly Significant
Normative Commitment	0.709**	<.001	Highly Significant
Continuance	0.920**	<.001	Highly Significant

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

As seen in the table, the computed rho-values ranging from 0.407 to 0.920 indicate a moderate to very strong direct relationship among the sub variables of work engagement and organizational

commitment. There was a statistically significant relationship between work engagement and organizational commitment because the obtained p-values were less than 0.01.

Table 14
Relationship Between Work Engagement and Employee's Development Programs

Variables	rho	p-value	Interpretation
Physical Engagement			
Knowledge and Skills Retention	0.673**	<.001	Highly Significant
Significance of Programs	0.638**	<.001	Highly Significant
Employees' Appreciation	0.647**	<.001	Highly Significant
Cognitive Engagement			
Knowledge and Skills Retention	0.690**	<.001	Highly Significant
Significance of Programs	0.693**	<.001	Highly Significant
Employees' Appreciation	0.685**	<.001	Highly Significant
Emotional Engagement			
Knowledge and Skills Retention	0.556**	<.001	Highly Significant
Significance of Programs	0.418**	<.001	Highly Significant
Employees' Appreciation	0.474**	<.001	Highly Significant

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

As seen in the table, the computed rho-values ranging from 0.418 to 0.693 indicate a moderate to strong direct relationship among the sub variables of work engagement and employee's development programs. There was a statistically significant relationship between work engagement and employee's development programs because the obtained p-values were less than 0.01.

Table 15
Relationship Between Organizational Commitment and Employee's Development Programs

Variables	rho	p-value	Interpretation
Affective Commitment			
Knowledge and Skills Retention	0.689**	<.001	Highly Significant
Significance of Programs	0.658**	<.001	Highly Significant
Employees' Appreciation	0.710**	<.001	Highly Significant
Normative Commitment			
Knowledge and Skills Retention	0.621**	<.001	Highly Significant
Significance of Programs	0.481**	<.001	Highly Significant
Employees' Appreciation	0.501**	<.001	Highly Significant
Continuance			
Knowledge and Skills Retention	0.538**	<.001	Highly Significant

Significance of Programs	0.456**	<.001	Highly Significant
Employees' Appreciation	0.461**	<.001	Highly Significant

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

As seen in the table, the computed rho-values ranging from 0.456 to 0.710 indicate a moderate to strong direct relationship among the sub variables of organizational commitment and employee's development programs. There was a statistically significant relationship between organizational commitment and employee's development programs because the obtained p-values were less than 0.01.

DISCUSSION

Table 1 delivers a thorough investigation of work engagement, specifically focusing on physical engagement. The respondents' perspectives are measured across five distinct indicators, each assigned a weighted mean (WM) score. The overall composite mean for all five indicators records at 3.05, positioning it within the "Agree" range. This implies a collective consensus among respondents concerning their physical engagement in the workplace. The weighted mean score reflects a positive evaluation of employees' involvement in physical aspects of their work. The "Agree" categorization suggests a shared acknowledgment of active participation, indicating a positive alignment between the workforce and their physical engagement at work. This comprehensive overview serves as a valuable insight into the employees' perceptions, highlighting a generally favorable assessment of their physical involvement in the work environment.

It is important to note that the highest-ranking indicator, with a WM of 3.66, is "I recognize the importance of reporting for work," and the respondents expressed a "Strongly Agree" sentiment towards this aspect of Physical Work Engagement. This signifies that there is a high level of acknowledgment among the respondents regarding the significance of punctuality and attendance (Sijabat, 2023). This indicator also can be considered as the "Task Completion" indicator of this facet of Work Engagement. The strong agreement expressed by the respondents in recognizing the importance of reporting for work suggests a communal understanding of the connection between punctuality and overall work engagement. This resonates with the concept of work engagement, a term popularized by Kahn in 1990, which posits that employees invest not only their physical but also their mental efforts in the execution of their tasks at work.

The indicator "Maintaining an active presence in my workplace" secures the second position with a WM of 3.39. This signifies a unanimous agreement among respondents with this aspect of Physical Engagement. The obtained result indicates a prevalent inclination among respondents to actively engage in workplace activities, underscoring a significant inclination for Work Engagement. The consensus observed among the surveyed individuals implies a highly favorable disposition towards their professional involvement. This unanimous agreement across the employee spectrum not only underscores a positive work environment but also signifies that employees are

consistently and energetically executing their duties and responsibilities. Such active participation contributes significantly to fostering a collective sense of engagement within the organizational framework (Abdulrahman, et al., 2022). The widespread commitment to workplace involvement suggests that individuals are not merely fulfilling their roles but are also actively contributing to the overall productivity and success of the team or organization.

However, it is notable that while the majority of indicators fall within the "Agree" range, there is variation in the degree of agreement among respondents. For instance, the indicators "I am enthusiastic about work and doing my duties" and "I am willing to participate in the activities at work" have lower weighted means of 2.61 and 2.65, respectively. These places the two indicators in the "Agree" range but towards the lower end of the spectrum. This submits that there is somewhat tempered enthusiasm among respondents when it comes to their duties. This, therefore indicates a potential area for improvement in fostering greater enthusiasm and work engagement within the three host organizations.

The majority of indicators for Physical Engagement reflect a positive work engagement, particularly in terms of recognizing the importance of reporting for work and staying active in the workplace. However, the nuanced disparities in agreement levels across different the five indicators highlight specific areas that may warrant further improvement. Elevating and refining Physical Engagement can cultivate a more engaged workforce and better work culture (Abidin, et al., 2021).

Table 2 shows that positive Cognitive Work Engagement is evident in the composite mean within the "Agree" range. This highlights laudable aspects of task completion efficiency and decision-making autonomy within the organizations of the respondents. These aspects can be considered as strengths that underscore a well-functioning and proactive work environment (Huang, et al., 2022). The efficiency in task completion signifies that the employees are capable of meeting objectives on time, while decision-making independence shows a level of empowerment and responsibility among employees within the pharmaceutical companies. The Composite Mean also reiterates that positive Cognitive Work Engagement enhances job performance, motivation, adaptability, job satisfaction, and overall organizational pursuits. (Amrollahifar, et al., 2023).

The assessment of work engagement, specifically focusing on cognitive engagement, reveals valuable perceptions into various facets of the total employee experience in an (Huang, et al., 2022). Based on the results from respondents, the competence in task accomplishment is deemed creditable. The majority of the respondents of the pharmaceutical companies expressed strong agreement that they consistently finish assigned tasks in a timely manner. This is reflected on indicator leading to the top rank in this Cognitive Engagement. This overwhelming consensus suggests a

positive trend in meeting work deadlines and underscores a communal commitment to the prompt delivery of responsibilities.

The high level of agreement among participants further strengthens the reliability and effectiveness of the team or individuals in question (Dawson, et al., 2019). The acknowledgement of this efficiency bodes well for the overall productivity and success of the tasks at hand. The emphasis on timely task completion not only highlights a disciplined work ethic and engagement but also signals a dedication to fulfilling professional obligations on a timely manner. This positive assessment indicates that the surveyed group exhibits a commendable level of time management and organizational skills, underwriting significantly to the overall effectiveness of the employees' work (Huang, et al., 2022). The strong majority's confirmation of timely task completion reflects a positive work culture and commitment to achieving goals.

On a positive note, employees feel empowered in their decision-making processes, with a substantial number strongly agreeing that they can decide on the best course of action to complete their assigned at work. This autonomy in decision-making is a notable asset contributing to overall work engagement within the organizational (Kim, et al., 2020). The challenge of detaching from the job is recognized by the respondents. The majority of the respondents agree that it is difficult to distance themselves from their work. While dedication to one's job is commendable, addressing this difficulty in detachment plays a crucial role in preventing potential burnout and promoting a healthier work-life balance.

Table 3 shows the assessment of work engagement focusing on emotional engagement. The Composite mean of Emotional Engagement is 3.22 which falls under the "Agree" range. This reflects a positive emotional work engagement among the respondents within their organizations. However, there are areas of improvement that can be addressed to enhance the efficiency of the organizations. Consistent feedback and strategic interventions grounded on these insights can further nurture a thriving and emotionally connected and engaged employees within the workplace. It reveals a generally positive sentiment among employees. Notably, the indicator which displays employees expresses a strong sense of personal accomplishment ranks the highest. Employees who are expressing a strong sense of personal accomplishment in organizations suggest high satisfaction and pride in their work at their organizations (Metz , 2018). In this light, Emotional Work Engagement can attribute to the overall success of completing tasks, achieving goals, and contributing meaningfully to the organization by the employee. This is reinforced by the second highest indicator: satisfaction with their current work or job. Acknowledgment, challenging work, goal attainment, autonomy, continuous learning, alignment with values, a encouraging work environment, and a vigorous work-life balance are key factors affecting this type of engagement (Selvi & Aiswarya, 2023). This creates a positive impact on both employees and the organization as a whole.

Employees perceive opportunities for professional growth and career development is placed third among the indicators. The mean score indicates that there is room for improvement in this area, signaling a potential gap between employee expectations and the current offerings. Enhancing initiatives for career advancement and skill development could contribute to even higher levels of engagement (Bai & Liu, 2018). Additionally, the indicator concerning working relationships with co-workers which ranked fourth implies a positive but not exceptional dynamic. This suggests that employees generally experience a good and harmonious working relationship with their colleagues, but it does not foster in the ideal level. The greater Emotional Work Engagement helps foster in an encouraging and constructive work culture, dynamics, and environment (Tharika, et al., 2022), Positive relationships among employees tender a positive emotional engagement at work. When employees have good relationships among their fellow coworkers, it fosters a holistic and collaborative work environment (Abdulrahman, et al., 2022). Employees who feel a sense of belonging and understanding with their coworkers are more likely to be emotionally engaged in their work. This emotional engagement can lead to increased job satisfaction, productivity, and overall well-being. It creates a workplace that fosters in a feeling of being valued, heard, and motivated which ultimately contributes to a positive work environment. Strong interpersonal relationships lay the foundation for a healthy emotional link which enhances the overall employee experience within the organization (Muda & Chan, 2020).

On the other hand, the indicator related to inspiration from work which ranks the last among the indicators reveals a slightly lower score which suggests that employees find room for development in feeling inspired by their tasks within their organization. Encouraging a more inspiring work culture and recognizing contributions of the employees could positively impact employees' motivation within the organization (Amrollahifar, et al., 2023). Creating an environment that values innovation and recognizes individual efforts by the employees cultivates a sense of purpose and achievement. This drives employees to excel in their work and improving overall workplace fulfilment and efficiency.

Table 4 provides an overview of work engagement across three key result in different aspects: Physical Engagement, Cognitive Engagement, and Emotional Engagement. Grand Composite Mean, with an overall average of 3.15, indicates an overall agreeable level of work engagement across all key areas within the organizations. This collective score proposes that employees within the three host organizations exhibit positive engagement in their work, encompassing the three aspects: physical, cognitive, and emotional. The balanced nature of this mean shows a rounded and satisfactory work environment where employees are likely to feel connected, mentally stimulated, and emotionally invested in their roles. The analysis highlights a generally positive work engagement across the organization. However, it also reveals specific areas for improvement, particularly in Physical and Cognitive Engagement aspect aspects.

Emotional Engagement, having the highest mean score of 3.22, underscores a strong agreement among employees, highlighting a profound connection and

commitment to the host organizations on an emotional level. The strong alignment emotionally suggests that employees feel a deep sense of belonging and investment in the three host organizations missions and values (Abdulrahman, et al., 2022). Recognizing and fostering this aspect becomes critical for organizations aiming to enhance employee satisfaction and productivity. Programs fostering a positive company culture, providing possible avenues for employee recognition, and ensuring effective communication channels within the workplace can further strengthen emotional engagement (Selvi & Aiswarya, 2023). This creates an environment where individuals are professionally committed and emotionally engaged in contributing to their organization's overall success.

Cognitive Engagement, marked by a mean score of 3.19, shows a better level of agreement compared to Physical Engagement within the organizations. Employees within the organization appear to have a positively engaged inclination towards tasks demanding mental effort. This indicates a strong placement with the cognitive aspects of their work (Li & Bunchapattanasakda, 2019). It being the second ranked indicator implies that while the overall engagement has a promising outlook, there may be specific areas for enhancement or opportunities to introduce further intellectual challenges. The three host organizations could explore development programs for skill enhancement, advanced training programs, or projects that stimulate employees' intellectual curiosity. Recognizing the issues and looking for ways to address them can enhance cognitive engagement and also contribute to a more active and intellectually stimulating work environment, enabling continuous growth and development among the employees of the organizations (Huang, et al., 2022).

The Physical Engagement aspect, with a mean score of 3.05, displays a largely agreeable but not outstanding level of engagement among the employees within their respective organizations. While there is a positive outlook towards physical engagement aspects of work, being the lowest ranked indicator implies that there is room for improvement. The organizations should strategically address this by implementing initiatives to enhance physical engagement. This could include encouraging a healthier work environment, regular breaks, and providing tailored solutions to ensure that the employees are comfortable and supported in their work within the organization (Chigeda, et al., 2022). By prioritizing addressing the issues, these organizations can positively impact employee well-being, satisfaction, and overall productivity. This leads to creating a workplace that improves the physical aspects of engagement for a more rounded and beneficial work environment for the employees (Kim, et al., 2020).

Table 5 shows an inclusive assessment of organizational commitment, specifically focusing on the affective commitment aspect. With a Composite Mean of 3.19, there is an overall agreement among the respondents which indicates a positive organizational commitment level. The individual indicators offer nuanced insights into specific facets of affective commitment. This guides potential organizational strategies and programs to further deepen the commitment of the employees.

The indicator "I feel this organization makes me feel like I am part of a family" is ranked highest with a WM of 3.70. This high score highlights a vigorous emotional connection among employees within the host organizations which transcends the conventional workplace dynamic and environment (Chigeda, et al., 2022). This accentuates a constructive organizational culture that dynamically nurtures a genuine sense of belonging. The cohesive and supportive environment, seen in employees' strong agreement in this indicator, goes beyond the conventional workplace dynamics within the organizations (Adewoyin, et al., 2020). As an alternative, it suggests that employees perceive the organization as more than just a place where they work but the organizations are seen as an extended family. This observation confirms a commendable commitment by the organizations to fostering meaningful connections among its employees which contributes to an organizational culture that prioritizes emotional connection and a sense of community (Khan, et al., 2021).

"I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career in this organization," has a WM of 3.42, claiming the second-ranking position among the indicators. This score emphasizes a notable inclination among employees to commit to long-term careers within their respective organizations. This reveals a positive disposition toward continuous dedication of the employees (Alrowwad, et al., 2019). This also signifies a significant alignment with the three host organizations' values and vision, indicating that the employees are generally contented within the organizations. The optimistic connection between the employees' individual career objectives and organizational values contributes to a positive work environment which fosters a sense of fulfillment among the employees (Fako, et al., 2018) This is also reflected in the third ranking indicator "I really feel as if this organization's problems are my own," which has a WM of 2.97. The result WM highlights a shared sense of responsibility among employees. This shows a collective commitment to addressing organizational challenges met by their respective organizations. This suggests a positive organizational attitude wherein the organizations' employees feel they are personally invested in overcoming problems, fostering a collaborative approach to problem-solving within their work environment (Kassaw & Golga, 2019).

The lowest ranked indicators are tied between "I feel that I am 'emotionally attached' to this organization" and "I have a strong sense of belonging in my organization" sharing the same WM of 2.93 revealing a moderate level of agreement. Both of these indicators address emotional attachment and a sense of belonging of the organizations' employees. While the verbal interpretation "Agree" still indicates positivity, these indicators suggest areas where the organization could enhance emotional ties and strengthen the sense of belonging among employees. Emotional connection and attachment cultivate devotion, commitment, and a sense of reason among the employees of the organization (Khan, et al., 2021). The host organizations should consider targeted interventions and development programs to distinguish and reinforce each of this aspect to further nurture their employees' connection to the workplace.

Table 6 provides an inclusive overview of organizational commitment measured through its normative commitment aspect. The composite mean of all indicators is 3.39 which places it within the “Agree” range. This shows a generally optimistic normative commitment among the employees of the host institution, with robust sense of agreement on the difficulty of leaving, perceived inadequate alternatives, and acknowledgment of personal costs in leaving. This overall agreement within the employees reinforces the notion that employees, on average, feel a substantial normative commitment to the organization (Nguyen, et al., 2020).

This aspect of organizational commitment refers to an employee's sense of obligation to remain with the organization due to a perceived necessity or desire (Kalitanyi, 2022). The indicators shed light on employees' sentiments regarding the exertion needed if they leave their current job, the impact on various life facets if they do, their certainty in the necessity and desire to stay, the seeming lack of alternative opportunities, and the acknowledgment of the employees' personal sacrifices associated with leaving the organization.

The indicator, "I believe I have not enough options to consider leaving this organization," has the highest WM of 3.99 which is within the “Strongly Agree” range. This indicates a robust consensus among employees that they perceive limited alternatives if they leave their current organization. This can possibly be attributed to factors such as the employee's specialized skills, job market conditions, or an optimistic outlook of the employee's current work environment (Nitafan, 2020). Positive work cultures, effective leadership, and a supportive organizational climate contribute to employees viewing their current engagement optimistically. When employees have a positive experience in their current work, they may be less motivated to explore other opportunities (Adewoyin, et al., 2020).

"It would be very hard for me to leave my job at this organization right now even if I wanted to," has a weighted mean (WM) of 3.60, indicating a robust level of agreement and is ranked second among the indicators. This suggests that a substantial percentage of employees feels a strong attachment to their organization, making it difficult for them to consider the idea of voluntarily leaving. This could be indicative of a positive organizational culture, strong leadership, or fulfilling work experiences (Kuhai, et al., 2020). This idea is also highlighted by the indicator, "Leaving this organization would require a considerable personal sacrifice from me is one of the reasons why I continue to work here." This indicator has a WM of 3.23, falling into the Agree range. This suggests that employees recognize the personal disadvantages associated with leaving the organization which ultimately contributes to their decision to stay (Candelario, et al., 2020).

The second lowest and lowest ranked indicators are "I believe that staying with this organization is a matter of necessity and desire," and "Different aspects of my life would be affected if I left this organization," respectively. They have a WM of 3.19 and

2.93, respectively, which puts them together in the Agree range. While the agreement of the employees with the indicator is present, it is not as pronounced as the other indicators. This implies that employees recognize the effect of leaving but may not perceive it as strongly as the difficulty of leaving the organization (Kalitanyi, 2022). Employees that show a sense of obligation and desire to stay, suggests a combination of both intrinsic motivation and external issues inducing their commitment to the organization.

Table 7 presents a nuanced analysis of organizational commitment through the continuance commitment aspect. The composite mean of all indicators is 3.26 which places it within the “Agree” range. This reveals a strong sense of continuance commitment among the employees within the host institutions with a mostly high agreement on the sense of obligation as an important factor in their decision to stay in their organization. The presence of ethical considerations, emotional ties, and perceptions of organizational worthiness adds depth to the understanding of employees' commitment (Colquitt, et al., 2021).

This is the aspect of the organizational commitment wherein employees may feel compelled to stay with their organization due to perceived costs or their sense of obligation (Kassaw & Golga, 2019). The indicators for this aspect highlight the employees' sentiments regarding the perceived properness of leaving, feelings of guilt linked with leaving the organizations, the commendable nature of the organizations' loyalty, the sense of responsibility to stay, and the indebtedness employees' impression towards their organization.

The indicator, "I would not leave my organization right now because of my sense of obligation to it," has the highest WM of 3.51 which falls into the “Strongly Agree” range. This indicates a definitive consensus among employees that their sense of obligation is a significant factor in their decision to stay. This line up with the fundamental notion of continuance commitment wherein employees feel they are bound to the organization due to perceived costs, such as the time, effort, or resources invested (Kasogela, 2019). This idea is complemented by the second and third ranking indicator; both falling into the “Agree” range. The indicator "I would have a feeling of guilt if I left this organization now" has a WM of 3.40. The presence of guilt as an aspect in the choice to leave by an employee shows a strong emotional tie to their organization (Colquitt, et al., 2021). This emotional tie contributes to the continuance commitment, as employees have a sense of fear for negative sentiments associated with abandoning their current roles in their organization. The third ranking indicator, "I do not feel it would be right to leave even if leaving would be better for me," has WM of 3.38. This suggests that employees recognize a struggle between what may be personally advantageous and what is perceived as ethically right (Abellanosa, et al., 2020). This inner struggle of an employee can create a sense of moral responsibility to continue which indicates a form of continuance commitment.

Lowest ranking indicators are "I owe a great deal to this organization," which has a WM of 3.08, and "This organization deserves my loyalty," which has a WM of 2.94. Both of the categories within the mid "Agree" range. While the agreement is present, the lower mean suggests a more nuanced standpoint among employees regarding the organizations' right for the loyalty of their employees (Al-Jabri & Ghazzawi, 2019). The first indicator probes into the perception of the organization's actions, policies, or values that warrant employees' commitment. The second indicator suggests that employees recognize a debt to the organization, possibly stemming from the opportunities, support, or growth they have experienced (Chidega, et al., 2022). Recognizing and addressing this personal obligation an employee has to the organization can further reinforce the sense of continuance commitment.

Table 8 presents a wide-ranging summary of the different aspects of organizational commitment. The Grand Composite Mean of the Organizational Commitment is 3.28 which still falls under the "Agree" range. Organizational commitment is a vital aspect of an employee's connection and loyalty to the organization they are part of (Candelario, et al., 2020). The table comprises three key dimensions of commitment: Affective Commitment, Normative Commitment, and Continuance. Additionally, it makes available the Grand Composite Mean which offers an overall perspective on the level of agreement within the employees regarding organizational commitment.

Normative Commitment emerges as the highest-ranked dimension with a Composite Mean of 3.39 which signals a stronger agreement within the workforce. Normative Commitment is associated with a sense of obligation or moral responsibility of an employee towards his or her organization (Kalitanyi, 2022). The Composite Mean is within the "Agree" range. This higher level of commitment may be indicative of the employees' feeling of moral obligation to stay with the organization; possibly owing to shared values, positive organizational culture, or a sense of duty (Mezeh, 2021). The employees, driven by a shared understanding of principles, an optimistic organizational culture, or a sincere sense of responsibility, demonstrate a commitment that exceeds the contractual or transactional dimension of employment.

Continuance, with a Composite Mean of 3.26 (putting it in the "Agree" range) and the second ranking dimension, demonstrates a commendable level of agreement among the respondents. This dimension of commitment is concerned about the perceived costs of employees associated with leaving the organization (Kalitanyi, 2022). The recognition of value and benefits made available from staying with the organization likely contributes immensely to the observed commitment within the employees. They may perceive tangible and intangible compensations, such as career growth opportunities, financial stability, or a constructive work environment, which influence their overall commitment level to the organization. This realistic perspective on commitment proposes that employees are making a rational assessment of the costs and benefits associated with their organizational tenure (Chidega, et al., 2022).

Affective Commitment, with a Composite Mean of 3.19, emphasizes a generally positive and favorable sentiment among employees towards their respective organizations. This dimension digs into the emotional attachment and identification that employees feel for their workplace (Adewoyin, et al. 2020). Despite its mean being slightly lower compared to the other aspects of commitment dimensions, it resides within the “Agree” which signifies a notable level of positive emotional connection and commitment. Furthermore, Affective commitment comprises the employees' notion of loyalty, affection, and belongingness to their organizations (Chidega, et al., 2022). The emotional connection within the three host organizations may stem from various foundations such as a supportive work environment, positive relationships with coworkers, or a strong connection with the organization's values and mission.

Table 9 presents the analysis of Employee Development Programs with a specific focus on Knowledge and Skills Retention dimension. The Composite Mean of 3.00, which falls within the “Agree” range, provides an aggregated view of employees' sentiments regarding the Employee Development Programs' effectiveness in terms of Knowledge and Skills Retention. This shows a collective agreement that the organizations' programs contribute positively to employees' professional growth (Al-Rawahi, 2022). It mirrors a consensus that the initiatives executed by these organizations contribute meaningfully to enhancing the skills, knowledge, and overall growth of their workforce. The table includes five key indicators offering valuable insights about the employees' notion on the effectiveness and impact of the organization's developmental initiatives towards them.

"I learned new skills from programs instituted by my organization" indicator boasts the highest WM of 3.37 among the indicators of this dimension. This indicates a strong consensus among employees of the three host organizations that they have learned new skills through the programs instituted by their respective organizations. Its WM falling under the “Agree” range aligns with its high score; reflecting the success of the organizations in fostering skill development programs. The indicator being ranked as the highest accentuates the effectiveness of these programs in imparting valuable skills to the employees. By aligning closely with the developing demands of their industry, the organizations cater to the dynamic needs of employees: ensuring technical proficiency and honing of crucial soft skills (Mishra, 2023). This position underscores a commitment by the organizations to create a supportive environment. This also compliments the second highest indicator; "I value the knowledge and skills I gain from my organization's programs." This indicator has a WM of 3.24 which falls under the “Agree” range. This indicator underscores that employees give importance on the knowledge and skills acquired through the organization's programs. This emphasizes the positive perception of the overall influence of these developmental programs on the professional growth and competence of the employees (Mishra, 2023).

"I apply things I learn from the programs of my institution" is the third highest and has WM of 2.81 which falls under the “Agree” range. Employees confirm their application of knowledge and skills gained from their respective organizations' programs. While there

is a level of agreement on the practical application of the acquired knowledge, there may be variations in the extent to which the employees implement these learnings in their daily roles (Bhanudas, 2021). The differences in the extent of implementation shows the complexity of translating learning into action in diverse professional contexts within the organizations.

The alignment between the skills acquired and the actual requirements of the job and this can be seen in the indicator "I find the learnings from previous programs still applicable today." With a WM of 2.79 and falling under the "Agree" range, employees of the host organizations generally recognize the continuing relevance of learnings from past programs. However, the fourth rank suggests that there is room for improvement in ensuring the sustained applicability of these acquired knowledge and skills over time. This indicator highlights the need of the organizations to focus on improving the enduring value of the knowledge imparted through the organizations' developmental programs (Yedama, et al., 2020). This is also highlighted by the lowest ranking indicator; "I still use skills I've learned from previous programs." While employees generally agree (WM of 2.77) that they continue to use skills and knowledge acquired from previous developmental programs, the lowest rank suggests a potential challenge in retaining and applying these skills over time. This indicator provokes a deeper investigation into the factors prompting the sustainability of skills gained through developmental programs (Mishra, 2023).

Table 10 provides an in-depth examination of Employee Development Programs, focusing on the aspect of Significance of Programs. This aspect Composite Mean of 3.08 falls within the "Agree" range which provides an overall assessment of employees' sentiments regarding the Significance of Employee Development Programs. This is indicative of a collective understanding that the host organizations' programs are largely perceived as relevant, utilizable, and address needs to enhance efficiency and productivity (Al-Rawahi, 2022). This shared perspective highlights a cohesive statement regarding the relevance and utility of the organization's endeavors, fostering a positive environment where programs are not only acknowledged but positively accepted for the programs' role in improving performance and meeting organizational needs. The table includes five key indicators emphasizing valuable insights into how employees perceive the relevance and impact of the organization's developmental programs on their specialized roles and expectations.

"The programs in my organization aid me while doing tasks at work" has the highest WM of 3.35 in this aspect. This indicator stands out as one that is particularly impactful. Employees categorically agree that the programs initiated by the organizations help them in performing their tasks at work; emphasizing the practical value of these programs in improving job performance (Oluwaseun, 2018). The acknowledgment that these programs dynamically aid in task execution reflects their tangible and positive effect on job performance. This notion is reiterated by the "The programs in my organization address my needs and that of others to be more efficient and effective at performing my tasks" indicator which has the second highest WM of 3.24. This indicator underscores

that employees see the programs as relevant in addressing their needs and contributing to enhancing efficiency and effectiveness in their task performance (De Jesus & Fajardo, 2022).

The third ranking indicator, "I find the programs in my organization are utilizable even outside my work," has a WM of 3.12 which emphasizes that employees see the training and developmental programs as not only relevant to their work but also applicable outside their professional roles. It gestures a cohesive bond between organizational training goals and the broader aspirations and needs of employees within the organization (Oluwaseun, 2018). This fosters a culture of learning that extends well beyond the confines of the organizations

"I find the programs in my organization highly relevant to my work" with a WM of 2.87 is the second lowest ranked indicator. This is startling given that the association of this indicator to the highest ranked indicator. However, this indicator still imposes that employees generally see the significance of programs to their work (Bilderback & Miller, 2023). However, its ranking suggests that there may be aspects where improvements could be made to improve the perceived relevance of these programs. This is reiterated by the lowest ranking indicator: "The programs in my organization align my expectations to that of my organization." While employees mostly agree (WM of 2.82) that the programs imposed by the organizations align their expectations with those of the organization, there is room for improvement in this aspect. Employees may not completely perceive a continuous and cohesive integration between their expectations and the goals of the organizational programs (Bhatt, 2020).

Table 11 provides an evaluation of Employee Development Programs in terms of Employees' Appreciation. The Composite Mean of 3.07 directs a generally optimistic consensus among employees regarding the impact of the programs by the organizations. This suggests that, on average, employees see the developmental programs initiated by the organizations as beneficial, contributing to various aspects of their professional growth and employment satisfaction (Al-Rawahi, 2022). This score is indicative of a positive alignment between the organizations' objectives and employees' experiences.

"The programs of my organization make me feel like I am part of the future of my organization as they prepare me for other tasks," stands out as an exceedingly impactful aspect of the employee development programs as the highest-ranking indicator. The WM of 3.23 emphasizes the host organizations programs' effectiveness in addressing current requirements of the workplace and fostering a sense of community and future readiness in the organizations. This result signifies that employees not only acknowledge the current utility of the programs and recognize their role in preparing employees for future challenges and tasks within the (Chidega, et al., 2022). "I am confident with performing my tasks after attending the programs of my organization," indicator reiterates the top indicator's notion. This indicator has a WM of 3.17 which falls within the "Agree" range. This indicator highlights the positive impact of the programs on employees' confidence

levels by emphasizing their perceived efficiency in improving the employees' work performance. This suggests that the programs implemented by the organization are not merely theoretical but are seen as practical, instilling a sense of assurance and confidence in employees as they execute their work (De Jesus & Fajardo, 2022).

"The programs of my organization help decide into staying with my organization," secures a WM of 3.08 as the third ranking indicator. This further affirms the overall agreement among employees on the programs' influence on employees' decision to stay with their respective organizations. This suggests that the developmental programs contribute a prominent role in shaping employees' commitment to staying with the organization (Magaji, et al., 2021). This alignment is essential as it highlights the programs not only as vehicles for skill enhancement but also as integral components in building a positive employee experience and organizational culture that contribute to an employee's long-term organizational commitment. Organizational commitment can be seen through the programs initiated by the organizations through the "I am satisfied with the work I am doing, and I feel like I am growing professionally when I attend the programs of my organization," indicator. This is the fourth-ranking indicator with a WM of 3.06. Although falling within the "Agree" range, its ranking suggests that there may be opportunities for enhancement to improve satisfaction and perceived professional growth by the employees. Ensuring that employees perceive tangible benefits from their engagement in the developmental programs is essential to further organizational commitment (Dachner, et al., 2019). Lastly, the indicator "I feel empowered after attending the employee development programs of my organization," obtains a Weighted Mean of 2.81 and is the lowest ranked indicator. This signals an agreement among the employees with the notion but with a slightly lower impact compared to other indicators. The result also reiterates the need for improving the programs to address overall satisfaction and appreciation of the employees with the training and developmental programs initiated by the organization.

Table 12 serves as a comprehensive summary of Employee Development Programs, encapsulating its three dimensions; significance of the programs, and overall employee appreciation. This overarching measure provides a consolidated view of the programs' effectiveness across the different dimensions. The Grand Composite Mean, stands at 3.05 which places it within the "Agree" range. The positive interpretation reflects a general acceptance among employees regarding the value and impact of the Employee Development Programs in their work environment. The high Composite Mean for the Significance of Programs shows its strategic importance, while the Employees' Appreciation dimension confirms the positive impact of these programs. The nuanced insights provided by the Knowledge and Skills Retention dimension point to opportunities for enhancement and refinement.

Significance of Programs has the highest Composite Mean of 3.08 which indicates a strong collective affirmation among employees regarding the importance and impact of the developmental programs by their respective organizations. This highlights the

strategic value of these programs which emphasizes their perceived significance in contributing to individual and overall organizational growth (De Jesus & Fajardo, 2022). It submits that these programs are seen as an instrumental part in shaping the collective mindset of the employees. This means aligning employees with the organization's vision and mission, and fostering a culture of continuous learning and adaptability. The significance of the programs in adding to individual and organizational growth has broader implications. It indicates that employees view these programs as more than just requirements of training sessions; instead, employees see them as transformative programs that contribute to their professional advancement and, by extension, the overall success of their respective organizations (Mishra, 2023).

Employees' Appreciation has Composite Mean of 3.07 which falls under the "Agree" range. This suggests an optimistic sentiment among employees within the organizations regarding the value and impact of the initiated programs. This positive sentiment goes beyond the mere acknowledgment of the programs' existence but rather, it implies that employees actively appreciate and value the programs as vital parts of their professional development (Tharanya, et al., 2020). Employees are not only participants but they are dynamic contributors to the positive account surrounding the impact of these programs on their overall professional satisfaction and growth.

Knowledge and Skills Retention dimension has the Composite Mean of 3.00 which falls within the "Agree" range. Being the lowest-ranking dimension, this suggests a moderate consensus among employees regarding the effectiveness of the programs in retaining knowledge and skills. While the "Agree" interpretation is positive, the organization may benefit from a nuanced examination of specific program components to enhance knowledge retention further. This recognition becomes a critical pivotal point for the leaders of the organization aiming to refine and optimize the impact of developmental programs on knowledge and skills retention (Yedama, et al., 2021). This insight underscores the organization's commitment to ensuring that developmental programs not only meet the current needs of employees but also evolve to align with changing expectations and advancements in knowledge acquisition.

Table 13 presents the Relationship Between Work Engagement and Organizational Commitment, exploring the correlation (ρ) and associated p-values for various subvariables or dimensions. The computed ρ -values, ranging from 0.407 to 0.920, indicate a moderate to very strong direct correlation among the subvariables of work engagement and organizational commitment. The significance level, as seen with the p-values ($<.001$), posits that there is a statistically substantial relationship between work engagement and organizational commitment.

Physical Engagement has high correlation coefficients indicating strong and statistically significant relationships with Affective Commitment ($\rho = 0.862$, $p < .001$), Normative Commitment ($\rho = 0.407$, $p < .001$), and Continuance ($\rho = 0.462$, $p < .001$). This suggests that employees who are further physically engaged in their work also

exhibit higher levels of affective, normative, and continuance commitment to the organization. This means that physical engagement nurtures a sense of connection between employees and the organization; employees feel more dedicated, integrated, and valued (Colquitt, et al., 2021). It enhances their motivation and energy, leading to increased job satisfaction and a stronger identification with organizational goals. This emotional bond reduces nonattendance and turnover rates which in turn, contributes to a more stable and productive work environment (Abidin, et al., 2021).

For Cognitive Engagement, a similar design appears with remarkably high correlation coefficients for Affective Commitment ($\rho = 0.833$, $p < .001$), Normative Commitment ($\rho = 0.462$, $p < .001$), and Continuance ($\rho = 0.584$, $p < .001$). This infers that employees who are mentally devoted in their work, displaying cognitive engagement, also establish stronger affective, normative, and continuance commitments. The consistency of highly significant correlations across all three dimensions of both work engagement and organizational commitment is noteworthy. This consistency reinforces the strength of the observed relationships and this highlights the interrelated nature of work Engagement and organizational Commitment. The strongest correlation between dimensions is observed between Emotional Engagement and Continuance Commitment ($\rho = 0.920$). This highlights a particularly compelling link between deep emotional connection to work and the perceived costs of leaving the organization. When employees exhibit a strong sense of emotional engagement and continuance commitment, turnover rates are likely lower due to the employees staying with the organization for both emotional and practical reasons (Abellanosa, et al., 2020). The employees shows a multifaceted sense of loyalty.

This correlation analysis also implies that developing work engagement in its different dimensions can significantly contribute to enhancing organizational commitment (Rani, et al., 2020). The real-world implications of this analysis are substantially beneficial for organizational leaders. The findings of this analysis emphasize that engaged employees are more likely to exhibit higher levels of organizational commitment. Organizations aiming to nurture dedicated employees should consider strategies or programs that promote physically and cognitive engagement, and programs that foster emotional connections to their work or affective commitment (Nabhan & Munajat, 2023).

Table 14 explores the relationship between work engagement and employee development programs. The table shows summarizing the overall findings, stating that the computed rho-values ranging from 0.418 to 0.693 indicate a moderate to strong direct relationship among the sub-variables or dimensions of work engagement and employee's development programs. There is a statistically significant relationship between these two variables as seen on the obtained p-values being less than 0.01. This value confirms a strong correlation between work engagement and employee development programs.

For physical engagement, the rho-values with the employee development programs variables of range from 0.638 to 0.673 and have all p-values less than 0.001.

This indicates an exceedingly noteworthy relationship implying a strong positive correlation between physical engagement and employee development programs. Moving to cognitive engagement, similar variables are considered. The rho-values range from 0.685 to 0.693, again with p-values less than 0.001. This suggests an exceedingly significant relationship; indicating a strong positive correlation between cognitive engagement and employee development programs.

Emotional engagement's strong correlations with knowledge and skills retention, significance of programs, and employees' appreciation is evident with rho-values ranging from 0.418 to 0.556 and p-values less than 0.001. This reinforces the conclusion of a highly substantial correlation between emotional engagement and employee development programs. Emotionally engaged employees are seen to have deeply connected to their learning experiences in the organization; leading to better retention of the knowledge and skills imposed by the program (Hajjar & Alkhanaizi, 2018). The enthusiasm and commitment of the employees instigates them to actively participate and learn in training and development programs. Emotionally engaged employees are seen to be more motivated to be updated and proficient in their roles (Wassem, et al., 2019).

Employees who perceive that the organization is committed to their long-term career growth and development are likely to reciprocate with higher levels of work engagement (Mrunali & Pathak, 2021). This commitment nurtures a positive work environment and establishes a mutual relationship wherein engaged employees contribute meaningfully to the organization's success. This entails that employee development programs align with individual employee career goals; employees are more likely to be engaged in their work (Dawson, Knight, & Patterson, 2019).

Table 15 presents the findings related to the relationship between organizational commitment and employee development programs. The analysis result suggests that there is a positive and substantial connection between organizational commitment and participation in employee development programs. The computed rho-values ranging from 0.456 to 0.710 show a moderate to strong direct connection among the sub-variables of organizational commitment and employee's development programs. The statistically significant relationships seen through its p-values being less than 0.01, confirming a strong connection between organizational commitment and employee development programs. This reiterates that employee development programs are a crucial component in fostering commitment and sense of loyalty with an organization's employees (Jehanzeb & Mohanty, 2018). This implies that when organizations invest in the personal and professional growth of their employees, the message that they value and support their staff is clear.

For affective commitment, the dimensions considered are knowledge and skills retention, significance of programs, and employees' appreciation with their rho-values range from 0.658 to 0.710 and with all p-values less than 0.001. This suggests a highly significant connection. Employees who are emotionally attached to their organization are

more likely to participate in and appreciate the organization's programs. Employees with a strong sense of affective commitment are seen to be more invested in their learning programs and retention of knowledge and skills (Bai & Liu, 2018). The employees' emotional commitment to the organization propels them to actively participate with development programs and apply new skills proficiently.

In the case of normative commitment, similar dimensions are examined. The rho-values range from 0.481 to 0.621 with p-values less than 0.001 which signifies a highly significant relationship. This suggests a positive correlation between normative commitment and employee development programs. Lastly, Continuance commitment shows strong correlations with knowledge and skills retention, significance of programs, and employees' appreciation, with the rho-values ranging from 0.456 to 0.538 and p-values less than 0.001. This suggests that employees who perceive high costs associated with leaving the organization are more likely to partake in the development programs of the organization. Employee development programs can foster in job satisfaction with the employees in an organization (Mrunali & Pathak, 2021). As employees obtain new skills and knowledge, they may experience increased job satisfaction and a perception of growth. This can lead to higher levels of affective commitment. Investing in employee development shows that the organization values its employees and is willing to support their professional advancement (Yedama, et al., 2021).

Organizations that prioritize employee development are seen to have higher retention rates. Employees who perceive that their organization is actively investing in their growth are more likely to stay with the organization longer. This nurtures continuance commitment, where employees remain with the organization because of the perceived costs associated with leaving (Bhanudas, 2021).

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher came up with the following conclusions:

1. There is strong evidence on the organizations work engagement in terms of physical, emotional, and cognitive aspects.
2. The employees manifested strong organizational commitment in terms of affective, normative, and continuance aspects.
3. The employee development programs are seen to have moderate evidence on its effect considering employee retention programs in terms of Knowledge and Skills Retention, Significance, and Employees' Appreciation.
4. There is a significant relationship among work engagement, organizational commitment, and employee development programs.
5. An employee retention framework was developed for Research and Development Companies. There is a strong positive correlation among each variable which contributes to a positive work environment. The amalgamation of dynamic engagement, robust commitment, and continuous development opportunities

creates a workplace where employees are motivated to stay, reducing employee turnover.

Figure 1. Proposed Framework for an Effective Employee Retention Program for Research and Development Companies specifically Pharmaceutical Companies engaged in the field

Based on the conclusions of the study, the researcher came up with the following recommendations:

1. The pharmaceutical companies through their Research and Development Departments may strengthen the rewards and recognition system of the organizations to encourage their employees to perform their duties in a more enthusiastic manner.
2. The companies may implement programs that promote a sense of community and connection within the organization.
3. Policymakers and leaders may continue to encourage their employees to participate in planning and decision-making in pertinent processes that affect the employees' work within the organization to foster in inclusivity.
4. The Human Resource department may improve the programs and institute amore future proof programs addressing the needs of the employees.
5. The organizations' human resource departments or organization leaders may use the proposed employee retention framework to improve the employee retention at research and development companies especially within the pharmaceutical industry

6. Future researchers may use other variables that could have similar effects on the work engagement, organizational commitment, and employee development and training programs of research and development companies especially within the pharmaceutical industry.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Permissions from the three host institutions were requested before initiating this study. Ethical considerations were observed during the conduct of the research work to ensure that all information that were collected were used for research purposes only to maintain the quality and integrity of the research. At the request of the three host institutions, they were not named through this study to protect their privacy.

The researcher properly cited the adopted questionnaires. The researcher ensured the confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents by not seeking their names, when they answer the questionnaires.

REFERENCES

- Abdul Kadir, N., Hoesni, S., & Nagalingam, U. (2019, August). The Mediating Role of Work Engagement in the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Organisational Commitment among Higher Education Institution Lecturers. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 18(8), 31-53. Retrieved April 1, 2023, from <https://www.ijlter.org/index.php/ijlter/article/download/1568/pdf>
- Abdulrahman, B., Qader, K., Jamil, D., Sabah, K., Gardi, B., & Anwer, S. (2022). Work engagement and its influence in boosting productivity. *International Journal of Language, Literature and Culture (IJLLC)*, 2(6), 30-41. Retrieved April 1, 2023
- Abellanosa, G. G., Bao, M., Garrillos, E. A., Lacubtan, I. B., Lacubatan, M. L., & Macauyag, D. S. (2020, June). ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AND WORK MOTIVATION OF GOVERNMENT EMPLOYEES. *International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management*, 02(12). Retrieved April 3, 2023
- Abidin, N., Adam, S., Jah, N., & Rahmat, N. (2021). Investigating Work Engagement at the Workplace. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 11(9), 409-420.
- Adewoyin, O. O., Opeke, R., Ikonne, C., & Madukoma, E. (2020, February). Affective, Continuance and Normative Organizational Commitment of Library Personnel in Nigerian Universities. *Journal of Information Science, Systems and Technology*, 4(1), 80-87. Retrieved April 3, 2023
- Al-Harthy, B., Yusof, R., & Hamid, A. (2022). A Conceptual Paper on Compensation and Benefits, Job Security, Work-Life Balance, Employee Retention and Localization in Oman. *Global Business and Management Research: An International Journal*, 14(3), 688-710.
- Alieto, E. O., & Rillo, R. M. (2018). Indirectness Markers in Korean and Persian English Essays: Implications for Teaching Writing to EFL Learners. *The Journal of*

- English as an International Language, 13(2.2), 169. Retrieved April 1, 2023, from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED596726.pdf>
- Al-Jabri, B., & Ghazzawi, I. (2019). Organizational Commitment: A Review of the Conceptual and Empirical Literature and a Research Agenda. *International Leadership Journal*, 78-119. Retrieved April 2, 2023
- Alkafafy, M., & Siddiqui, A. (2022). Employer Attraction & Employee Retention in the Pharmaceutical Industry of Egypt and Pakistan. Lund: Lund University School of Economics and Management. Retrieved September 8, 2023
- Al-Rawahi, M. (2022, June). A Research Study on the Impact of Training and Development on Employee Performance during Covid-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research (IJMSR)*, 1-10. Retrieved April 3, 2023, from <https://www.arcjournals.org/pdfs/ijmsr/v10-i7/1.pdf>
- Alrowwad, A., Almajali, D., Aqqad, N., Masa'deh, R., & Obeidat, B. (2019). The Role of Organizational Commitment in Enhancing Organizational Effectiveness. 33rd International Business Information Management Association Conference, (pp. 9133-9154). Granada, Spain. Retrieved April 2, 2023
- Amrollahifar, J., Ali, M., Mansor, Z., Jaharuddin, N., & Guo, Y. (2023). Cognitive, Emotional and Social Intelligence towards Job Performance: The Mediator Role of Work Engagement. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 13(7), 376-402.
- Andrianto, H., & Alsada, Y. (2019). The Conceptual Framework of Employee Absorption. *iJournals: International Journal of Social Relevance & Concern*, 7(1), 11-14. Retrieved April 1, 2023, from <http://ijournals.in/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/2.7108-Yasser-compressed.pdf>
- Ansari, M., Bhoje, R., Bhosale, S., & Rahim, K. (2022, July). A STUDY ON RESEARCH DESIGN AND ITS TYPES. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*, 09(07), 1132-1135. Retrieved April 1, 2023, from <https://www.irjet.net/archives/V9/i7/IRJET-V9I7216.pdf>
- Arcadio, A., Diola, D. D., & Distor, J. S. (2023). Work Engagement and Organizational Commitment of Employees in Cavite, Philippines. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 8(7), 1-14.
- Bai, J., & Liu, J. (2018). A Study on the Influence of Career Growth on Work Engagement among New Generation Employees. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 300-317.
- Basikin, B. (2007). Vigor, Dedication and Absorption: Work engagement among secondary school English. AARE 2007. Fremantle. Retrieved April 3, 2023, from <https://www.aare.edu.au/data/publications/2007/bas07349.pdf>
- Bhanudas, D. (2021). Impact Of Training And Development On Satisfaction Level Of Employees In Manufacturing Industries. *Ikogretim Online - Elementary Education Online*, 20(1), 4634-4642. Retrieved April 2, 2023, from <https://www.ilkogretim-online.org/fulltext/218-1641574817.pdf>
- Bhatt, D. (Ed.). (2020). Training and Development in Work Organizations. *Mukt Shabd Journal*, 9(4), 3164-3179. Retrieved April 3, 2023
- Bilderback, S., & Miller, G. (2023). Importance of employee development programs in business. *Journal of Management Development*.

- BOI. (2017, March). Philippine Pharmaceutical Industry Profile. Philippine Board of Investments. Philippine Board of Investments (BOI). Retrieved October 2023, from <https://www.insights10.com/report/philippines-pharmaceutical-market-analysis/>
- Candelario, L., Tindowen, D., Mendezabal, M., & Quilang, P. (2020). Organisational Commitment and Job Satisfaction among Government Employees. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 13(10), 1627-1643. Retrieved April 3, 2023
- Caredo, D. T., Pomida, A. M., Paradero, A. L., & Casinillo, L. F. (2022). Modeling Employee Retention Amidst COVID-19 Pandemic: An Econometric Approach. *Recoletos Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(1).
- Chaudhary, V. (2023). A Review of Employee Retention as a Strategy for Organizational Success. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Engineering and Management (IJSREM)*, 7(11).
- Chigeda, F., Ndofirepi, T., & Steyn, R. (2022). Continuance in organizational commitment: The role of emotional intelligence, work-life balance support, and work-related stress. Retrieved April 3, 2023, from <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/joe.22172>
- Colquitt, J., LePine, J., & Wesson, M. (2021). *Organizational Behavior: Improving Performance and Commitment in the Workplace* (7th ed.). McGraw Hill.
- Dachner, A., Ellingson, J. E., Noe, R. A., & Saxton, B. (2019). The future of employee development. *CORE*, 1-16. Retrieved April 2, 2023, from <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/289197727.pdf>
- Das, B. L., & Baruah, M. (2013, Nov.-Dec.). Employee Retention: A Review of Literature. *Journal of Business and Management*, 14(2), 8-16.
- Dawson, J., Knight, C., & Patterson, M. (2019). Work engagement interventions can be effective: A systematic review. *European Journal of Work and Organisational Psychology*, 28 (3), 348-372. Retrieved April 2, 2023
- De Jesus, F. S., & Fajardo, L. L. (2022). The Benefits of Training and Development Programs for Lending Organization Personnel: Basis for Development of Training Program. *IRA-International Journal of Management & Social Sciences*, 18(1), 13-32. Retrieved April 2, 2023, from <https://research-advances.org/index.php/RAJMSS/article/view/1688/1319>
- Du, H., Mo, L., & Guo, Y. (2017, October). Work engagement and job performance :the moderating role of perceived organizational support. *anales de psicología*, 708-713. Retrieved April 3, 2023, from https://scielo.isciii.es/pdf/ap/v33n3/psicologia_social2.pdf
- Edralin, D. (2011). Human Capital Development for Innovation in Asia: Training and Development Practices and Experiences of Philippine Large Companies. *Asia Pacific Business Review*, 17(2), 225-239.
- Fako, T. T., Nkhukhu-Orlando, E., Wilson, D. R., Forcheh, N., & Linn, J. G. (2018). Factors associated with organizational commitment of academic employees in Botswana. *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 10(6), 56-64. Retrieved April 3, 2023, from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1183987.pdf>

- Fishbein, M., & Ajzen, I. (1975). *Belief, Attitude, Intention and Behavior: An Introduction to Theory and Research*. Boston: Addison-Wesley.
- Gulzar, R. (2020, June). Impact Of Affective Commitment On Employee Performance Special Reference To The Fenda Communication And It -Ksa. *International Journal Of Management (Ijm)*, 11(6), 1440-1454.
- Hajjar, S., & Alkhanaizi, M. (2018, April-June). Exploring the Factors That Affect Employee Training Effectiveness: A Case Study in Bahrain. *SAGE Open*, 1-12. Retrieved April 3, 2023, from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/2158244018783033>
- Huang, S. Y., Huang, C.-H., & Chang, T.-W. (2022). A New Concept of Work Engagement Theory in Cognitive Engagement, Emotional Engagement, and Physical Engagement. *Frontiers in Psychology*.
- Ismail, F., & Owaida, N. (2023). A Key to Improve Workplaces Productivity. *Jurnal Penyelidikan Sains Sosial*, 6(18), 80-90.
- Jehanzeb, K., & Mohanty, J. (2018). Impact of employee development on job satisfaction and organizational commitment: Person-organization fit as moderator. *International Journal of Training and Development*, 22(10).
- Jugessur, Y. S. (2022). Reliability and Internal Consistency of data: Significance of Calculating Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient in Educational Research. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention (IJHSSI)*, 11(4), 9-14.
- Kahn, W. A. (1990). Psychological Conditions Of Personal Engagement And Disengagement At Work. *Academy of Management Journal*, 33(4), 692-724. Retrieved April 1, 2023, from <https://cygnetinstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/William-Kahn-Employee-Engagement.pdf>
- Kalitanyi, V. (2022). Role of normative commitment in fostering university employees' commitment. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 11(10), 34-35.
- Kasogela, O. K. (2019). The Impacts of Continuance Commitment to Job Performance;. *Advance Journal of Social Science*, 5(1), 93-100. Retrieved April 3, 2023
- Kassaw, E., & Golga, D. (2019). Employees' Organizational Commitment in Higher Educational Setting. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.20944/preprints201904.0029.v1>
- Khan, A., Bashir, F., Nasim, I., & Ahmad, R. (2021). Understanding Affective, Normative & Continuance Commitment through the Lens of Training & Development. *iRASD Journal of Management*, 3(2), 105-113. Retrieved April 3, 2023
- Khan, H., Rehmat, M., Butt, T., Farooqi, S., & Asim, J. (2020). Impact of transformational leadership on work performance, burnout and social loafing: a mediation model. *Future Business Journal*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-020-00043-8>
- Khan, J. (2015). The Role of Research and Development in Economic Growth: A Review. *Journal of Economics Bibliography*, 2(3), 128-133.
- Kim, W., Oh, J., Park, J., & Wood, J. (2020). The Relationship Between Work Engagement and Work-Life Balance in Organizations: A Review of the Empirical Research. SAGE Publications, 1-23. Retrieved April 1, 2023, from <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/327045828.pdf>
- Kuhail, A., Arabi, A., Mohamad Zaid, M., & Ismawi, N. (2020, December). Relationship between Affective Commitment, Continuance Commitment and Normative

- Commitment towards Job Performance. *Journal of Sustainable Management Studies*, 1(1), 19-27. Retrieved April 3, 2023, from <https://majmuah.com/journal/index.php/jsms/article/download/69/37/>
- Kumar, D., & Siddika, H. (2017, December). Benefits Of Training And Development Program On Employees' Performance: A Study With Special Reference To Banking Sector In Bangladesh. *International Journal Of Research - Granthaalayah*, 5(12), 77-88.
- Li, S., & Bunchapattanasakda, C. (2019). Employee Engagement: A Literature Review. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 9(1), 63-80. Retrieved April 3, 2023
- Magaji, N., Akpa, V. O., & Ogundiwin, I. J. (2021, September). Career Development, Job Security And Employee Retention: An Empirical Study Of Selected Private Universities In Ogun State Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce & Management*, XI(9), 416-433.
- Malinao, C. M., & Agustin, J. G. (2022). Retention, Satisfaction, and Motivation Enablers of a Higher Education Institution in the Philippines amidst Teacher Migration. *Puissant*, 718-735.
- Masadeh, M. (2012). Training, Education, Development And Learning: What Is The Difference? *European Scientific Journal*, 8(10), 62-68.
- Mezeh, A. (2021). Job Enrichment and Employee commitment of Indigenous Oil Servicing Companies in Rivers State. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 5(9), 9-18. Retrieved April 3, 2023, from <https://www.ajhssr.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/B21590918.pdf>
- Mishra, P. (2023). The Impact Of Learning And Development On Employee Retention In Organizations. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Engineering and Management*, 7(5), 1-4.
- Mrunali, T., & Pathak, A. (2021, May). A study on the effectiveness of training and development on employee's performance at JK Paper Ltd. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 9(5), 110-125. Retrieved April 3, 2023, from <https://ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2105860.pdf>
- Muda, A., & Chan, Y. (2020). Psychological Empowerment and Organisational Commitment among Academic Staff of Public Universities in Malaysia. Retrieved April 3, 2023, from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1267354.pdf>
- Nabhan, F., & Munajat, M. (2023). The role of work engagement and organizational commitment in improving job performance. *Cogent Business & Management*.
- NEDA. (2023). National Development Plan 2023 - 2008. Metro Manila: National Economic and Development Authority (NEDA).
- Nguyen, H., Le, Q., Tran, Q., Tran, T., Nguyen, T., & Nguyen, T. (2020). The Impact of Organizational Commitment on Employee Motivation: A Study in Vietnamese Enterprises. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(6), 439-447. Retrieved April 1, 2023, from <https://koreascience.kr/article/JAKO202017764018218.pdf>
- Nitafan, R. P. (2020, November-December). Employee Silence, Organizational Commitment, and Job Burnout of Regular Employees in Local Government Units in the Cotabato Province, Philippines: A Keystone for Intervention.

- International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences, 5(6), 1932-1948. Retrieved April 2, 2023
- Nkhukhu-Orlando, E., Brown, B., Wilson, D., Forcheh, N., Linn, J. G., & Fako, T. T. (2019). The affective commitment of academics in a university in Bostwana. *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 12(2), 12-19. Retrieved April 3, 2023, from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1212802.pdf>
- Noe, R. A. (2017). *Employee Training and Development 7th Edition*. New York City, New York: McGraw-Hill Education.
- NTRC. (2014). *Tax Contribution of the Philippine Pharmaceutical Industry*. National Tax Research Center. Retrieved September 6, 2023, from <https://serp-p.pids.gov.ph/publication/public/view?slug=tax-contribution-of-the-philippine-pharmaceutical-industry>
- OECD. (2015). *The Impact of R&D Investment on Economic Performance: A Review of the Econometric Evidence*. Paris: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). Retrieved 2023, from [https://one.oecd.org/document/DSTI/EAS/STP/NESTI\(2015\)8/en/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/DSTI/EAS/STP/NESTI(2015)8/en/pdf)
- Olaoye, I. (2021). The role of research and development (R&D) expenditure and governance on economic growth in selected African countries. *African Journal of Science, Technology, Innovation and Development*, 13(6), 663-670.
- Oluwaseun, O. (2018, March). *Employee Training And Development As A Model For Organizational Success*. *International Journal of Engineering Technologies and Management Research*, 181-189. Retrieved April 2, 2023.pdf
- Patriota, D. (2009). *Employee retention: An integrative view of Supportive Human Resource Practices and Perceived Organizational Suppo*. 1-45.
- Rani, S., Agustiani, H., Ardiwinata, M., & Purwono, R. (2020). *Work Engagement and Organizational Commitment in Private University*. 3rd International Conference on Psychology in Health, Educational, Social, and Organizational Settings (ICP-HESOS 2018) - Improving Mental Health and Harmony in Global Community (pp. 464-469). SCITEPRESS – Science and Technology Publications. Retrieved April 4, 2023, from <https://www.scitepress.org/Papers/2018/85909/85909.pdf>
- Rasdi, R., & Chen, Y. (2018, December). *People Management for Managing Employees' Retention in the Organizations*. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social*, 8(12), 499-509.
- Reyes, C. M., & Taguba, A. D. (2020). *A Profile of the Philippine Pharmaceutical Industry*. PCC Issues Paper(02). Retrieved August 5, 2023, from <https://www.phcc.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/PCC-Issues-Paper-2020-02-A-Profile-of-the-Philippine-Pharmaceutical-Industry.pdf>
- Sari, D., Yudiarmo, A., & Sinambela, F. (2021). *Work Engagement and Innovative Work Behavior: Meta-Analysis Study*. *International Conference on Psychological Studies* (pp. 359-366). Atlantis Press. Retrieved April 3, 2023, from <https://www.atlantis-press.com/article/125955819.pdf>
- Selvi, J., & Aiswarya. (2023). *Examining the relationship between emotional intelligence and work engagement of automobile sector employees in Chennai*. *Rajagiri Management Journal*, 17(2), 156-169.

- Shabani, A., Rajabi, S., & Ahmadi Teymourlo, A. (2022). Key Factors to Improve Pharmaceutical Industry's R&D Productivity: A Case Study of Iranian Pharmaceutical Holding. *Medical Journal of the Islamic Republic of Iran*. Retrieved 2023, from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9700404/>
- Sijabat, R. (2023). Questioning Work Engagement and Employee Engagement. *International Journal of Social Science and Education Research Studies*, 2405-2411.
- Silva, I., Dias, Á., & Pereira, L. F. (2023). Determinants of employee intention to stay: a generational multigroup. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*.
- Sinha, C., & Sinha, R. (2012). Factors Affecting Employee Retention: A Comparative Analysis of two Organizations from Heavy Engineering Industry. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 4(3), 145-162.
- Soltanisehat, L., Alizadeh, R., & Mehregan, N. (2019). Research and Development Investment and Productivity Growth in Firms with Different Levels of Technology. *Iranian Economic Review*, 23(4), 795-818.
- Szarowská, I. (2018). Importance of R&D expenditure for economic growth in selected CEE countries. *E+M Ekonomie a Management*, 108-124.
- Taber, K. S. (2018). The Use of Cronbach's Alpha When Developing and Reporting Research Instruments in Science Education. *Res Sci Educ*, 48(6), 1273–1296.
- Tharanya, V., Gajenderan, V., & Nawaz, N. (2020). Impact Of Employee Engagement On Organizational Commitment And Job Performance. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(4), 4051-4061. Retrieved April 3, 2023
- Tharika, S., Iddagoda, A., & Bulinska-Stangrecka, H. (2022). Employee Engagement and its Dynamics: An Empirical Study of an Information Technology Company Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Academe and Industry Research*.
- Varntanian, S. (2018). The role of R & D in the modern pharmaceutical industry – challenges and benefits.
- Wassem, M., Baig, S., Abrar, M., Hashim, M., Zia-Ur-Rehman, M., Awan, U., . . . Nawab, Y. (2019). Impact of Capacity Building and Managerial Support on Employees' Performance: The Moderating Role of Employees' Retention. *Sage Journals*, 9(3). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/215824401985995>
- Yedama, N. K., Kunchaparthi, S., & Surekha, G. (2021, August). Training and Development Program and its Benefits to Employee and Organization. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Cycle Research*, 13(8), 720-723. Retrieved April 3, 2023